

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL LITERACY IN REINFORCING VOCABULARY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSES

Haydarova Nargiza G'ulomjonovna
Prof University “Pedagogika va chet tillar”
kafedra o'qituvchisi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14249363>

Abstract. This article provides information about the effective use of modern technologies in increasing the vocabulary of students of English as a foreign language. In the article, the effectiveness of using various digital technologies and the effectiveness of traditional methods and non-traditional methods in increasing vocabulary was studied and analyzed. The main goal of the research is to improve the skills of using innovative methods and techniques to increase the vocabulary of English language learners with examples of the use of various electronic platforms and their effective results and some modern tools are given. The information of using most effective electronic tools for increasing vocabulary is given in a clear and complete way. Several useful aspects of the use of digital tools have been listed not only for those who are learning English as a foreign language and as a second language, but also for pedagogues who have been teaching English.

Keywords: tech tools, digital, vocabulary builder, vocabulary enhancement, traditional methods, non-traditional methods.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola chet tili sifatida ingliz tilini o'rganuvchilarning lug'at boyligini oshirishda zamonaviy texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanish haqida ma'lumot beradi. Maqolada turli raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish samaradorligi, an'anaviy va noan'anaviy usullarning lug'at boyligini oshirishdagi samarasi o'rganilib, tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi – turli elektron platformalar misolida innovatsion metodlar va usullardan foydalanish ko'nikmalarini yaxshilash, lug'at boyligini oshirishning samarali natijalari bilan tanishtirishdan iborat. Maqolada ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rganayotganlar uchun eng samarali elektron vositalardan foydalanish bo'yicha to'liq va aniq ma'lumotlar berilgan. Raqamli vositalardan foydalanishning bir nechta foydali jihatlari nafaqat ingliz tilini chet tili yoki ikkinchi til sifatida o'rganayotganlar, balki ingliz tilini o'qitib kelayotgan pedagoglar uchun ham sanab o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: texnologik vositalar, raqamli, lug'at boyligini oshirish, lug'atni kengaytirish, an'anaviy usullar, noan'anaviy usullar.

Аннотация. Это статья предоставляет информацию об эффективном использовании современных технологий для увеличения словарного запаса у студентов, изучающих английский язык как иностранный. В статье исследуется и анализируется эффективность использования различных цифровых технологий, а также традиционных и нетрадиционных методов в увеличении словарного запаса. Основная цель исследования — улучшить навыки применения инновационных методов и техник для расширения словарного запаса учащихся английского языка, приводя примеры использования различных электронных платформ и их эффективных результатов. В статье предоставлена четкая и полная информация о наиболее эффективных электронных инструментах для увеличения словарного запаса. Указаны несколько полезных аспектов использования цифровых инструментов не только для тех, кто изучает английский язык как иностранный или второй язык, но и для преподавателей, обучающих английскому языку.

Ключевые слова: технические инструменты, цифровые, расширение словарного запаса, улучшение словарного запаса, традиционные методы, нетрадиционные методы.

INTRODUCTION

In an era where digital literacy shapes every facet of learning and communication, its impact on vocabulary development represents a pivotal shift in English language education. As educators endeavor to navigate the intersection of technology and pedagogy, the potential for digital tools to enrich vocabulary learning has never been more significant. The essence of acquiring a robust vocabulary lies not just in traditional reading and rote memorization but in engaging, interactive, and personalized experiences that digital platforms afford. Thus, the role of digital literacy in advancing vocabulary development is crucial, paving the way for innovative teaching and learning practices that resonate with the digital natives of today.

This study will explore the fundamental concepts of digital literacy, emphasizing its importance and applicability in enhancing vocabulary development through various digital tools, such as word walls and other interactive means. It will further delve into practical strategies for integrating digital literacy into English language classes, highlighting the transformative potential of technology in vocabulary acquisition. By examining the impact of digital literacy on vocabulary growth, the discussion aims to provide educators with insights and methodologies to foster a more dynamic and effective learning environment. Through this comprehensive analysis, the article offers a roadmap for implementing digital literacy practices that elevate vocabulary learning to new heights, ensuring students not only understand the power of words but are also equipped to use them effectively in an increasingly digital world.

The number of publications on digital literacy has increased nearly tenfold during the past twenty years. Naturally, the wealth of scientific output is advantageous since it expands our understanding of the subject, but it also poses a serious challenge to academics: with so many studies conducted on the topic, it can be very challenging to fully comprehend the specifics and areas of interest within the field of study. Researchers gain by applying digital and quantitative research techniques to make sense of their field. To comprehend how research is arranged, Stopar & Bartol (2019), for instance, examine clusters of co-citations and co-citing sources. The goal of this research is to provide context for the wide range of writing on the subject of digital literacy in relation to education and learning.

The examination of Key Components of Digital Literacy in EFL classroom

Digital literacy in an English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom refers to the ability of students to effectively use digital tools and technologies to communicate, collaborate, create, and critically evaluate information in English. It encompasses a range of skills. Integrating digital literacy into the EFL classroom can enhance language learning by providing authentic contexts for communication, engaging students with multimedia resources, and fostering collaboration and creativity. Teachers can incorporate digital literacy activities into their lesson plans through project-based learning, online discussions, multimedia presentations, and virtual simulations, among other approaches. Exploring the key components of digital literacy within the EFL (English as a Foreign Language) classroom is crucial in today's technologically advanced world. This involves understanding how to effectively communicate using digital platforms such as email, messaging apps, and video conferencing tools. It also includes knowing the appropriate etiquette for online communication. Media literacy empowers individuals to engage actively in media-rich environments, participate in public discourse, and advocate for

media reform and social change (Kellner & Share, 2007). Digital communication skills encompass various abilities necessary for effective interaction in online environments. In the EFL classroom, fostering these skills can enhance students' proficiency in using English for digital communication purposes.

This might include creating multimedia presentations, digital artworks, or interactive projects. Understanding the ethical implications of using digital technology, including issues such as copyright infringement, digital rights, and online safety, is essential for responsible digital citizenship. Digital literacy also involves understanding how digital technologies shape and are shaped by different cultures and societies around the world.

Digital Literacy vs. Traditional Literacy in teaching vocabulary and comparing effectiveness of using both traditional and non-traditional methods

Digital literacy refers to the ability to access, understand, evaluate, and create information using digital technologies (Hague & Payton, 2010). Traditional literacy, on the other hand, typically refers to the ability to read, write, and comprehend written text in print form while **Traditional literacy** primarily involves print-based materials such as books, newspapers, and magazines. Digital literacy, however, encompasses a broader range of media, including websites, social media platforms, multimedia content, and online databases. Traditional literacy emphasizes reading and writing skills, while digital literacy includes skills such as navigating digital interfaces, conducting online research, critically evaluating online information for accuracy and credibility, and communicating effectively through digital mediums. Traditional literacy often requires physical access to printed materials, which may be limited by factors such as availability, cost, and geographical location. Digital literacy, on the other hand, can potentially overcome these barriers, as digital information is accessible online from virtually anywhere with an internet connection (Hargittai, 2010). Traditional literacy is often taught in formal educational settings such as schools and libraries, using textbooks and other printed materials. Digital literacy education, however, may occur both inside and outside the classroom, with online resources, interactive tutorials, and educational apps playing significant roles in instruction (Livingstone & Helsper, 2007). While traditional literacy remains fundamental, digital literacy has become increasingly important in today's technologically-driven society. The rapid proliferation of digital technologies has created new opportunities for accessing and sharing information but has also introduced challenges such as information overload, digital misinformation, and privacy concerns (Warschauer, 2016). Both traditional literacy and digital literacy are essential skills in the modern world. While traditional literacy lays the foundation for understanding written text, digital literacy enables individuals to navigate and critically engage with the vast array of information available in digital formats, thus empowering them to thrive in the digital age. Non-traditional methods tend to be more engaging for students due to their interactive and multimedia nature (Prensky, 2001). Technology-assisted learning, in particular, appeals to digital-native students who are accustomed to using digital devices in their daily lives. Research suggests that non-traditional methods can be as effective as, or even more effective than, traditional methods in promoting vocabulary retention (Hulstijn, 2001). The interactive and multisensory nature of non-traditional approaches may enhance encoding and retrieval processes, leading to better long-term retention of vocabulary. Both traditional and non-traditional methods have their merits in teaching vocabulary. Traditional methods provide a solid foundation in vocabulary basics and are often effective for initial exposure to new words. However, non-traditional methods offer innovative approaches that can enhance engagement, retention, and application of vocabulary in real-world contexts.

CONCLUSION

Digital literacy has a profound effect on vocabulary development, which is a significant change in English language education in a time when it influences all aspects of learning and communication. Never before has there been a greater opportunity to enhance vocabulary acquisition using digital tools as educators work to bridge the gap between pedagogy and technology. Building a strong vocabulary requires more than simply rote learning and reading aloud; it also requires the kind of individualized, dynamic, and engaging experiences that digital platforms provide. As a result, digital literacy plays a critical part in vocabulary development and opens the door to creative teaching and learning strategies that appeal to today's digital natives.

The essential ideas of digital literacy will be examined in this research, with a focus on how valuable and useful it is for improving vocabulary. This study report offers details on how students studying English as a second language can effectively expand their vocabulary through the use of contemporary technologies. The study examined and analyzed how well different digital technologies work as well as how well traditional and non-traditional techniques work for expanding vocabulary. Examples of how different electronic platforms are used, their successful outcomes, and some contemporary technologies are included in the study. There are comprehensive guidelines and recommendations for the application of contemporary techniques in teaching. Clear and comprehensive information about the best electronic tools for expanding vocabulary is provided in the second section of the study. There are a number of beneficial features of using digital tools that are highlighted for both teachers of English and students learning the language as a second or foreign language. The topic's literature was extensively consulted during the research process, and naturally, enough data was gathered from online sources.

REFERENCES

1. Hague, C., & Payton, S. (2010). Digital literacy across the curriculum. Futurelab.
2. Hulstijn, J. H. (2001). Intentional and incidental second language vocabulary learning: A reappraisal of elaboration, rehearsal, and automaticity. In P. Robinson (Ed.), *Cognition and second language instruction* (pp. 258–286). Cambridge University Press.
3. Hargittai, E. (2010). Digital na(t)ives? Variation in Internet skills and uses among members of the “Net Generation”. *Sociological Inquiry*, 80(1), 92-113.
4. Livingstone, S., & Bulger, M. E. (2014). *A Global Agenda for Children's Rights in the Digital Age: Recommendations for Developing UNICEF's Research Strategy*. London School of Economics and Political Science. Retrieved from <https://eprints.lse.ac.uk/60639/>
5. Kellner, D., & Share, J. (2007). Critical Media Literacy is Not an Option. *Learning Inquiry*, 1(1), 59–69. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11519-007-0004-8>
6. Prensky, M. (2001). Digital natives, digital immigrants part 1. *On the Horizon*, 9(5), 1–6.
7. Reinking, D., McKenna, M. C., Labbo, L. D., & Kieffer, R. D. (1998). Handbooks of literacy media and technology: A summary and an introduction. In D. Reinking, M. C. McKenna, L. D. Labbo, & R. D. Kieffer (Eds.), *Handbook of literacy and technology*:
8. Stopar, K., & Bartol, T. (2019). Digital competences, computer skills and information literacy in secondary education: Mapping and visualization of trends and concepts. *Scientometrics*, 118(2), 479–498 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-018-2990-5>
9. Warschauer, M. (2016). *Learning in the cloud: How (and why) to transform schools with digital media*. Teachers College Press.